

Systematic Review

The Use of Curcumin in the Treatment of Colorectal, Breast, Lung, and Prostate Cancers: An *in vivo* Study Update

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cancer is one of the most prevalent and complex diseases with diverse etiology and manifestations. Curcumin is a bioactive compound found in turmeric and could have therapeutic potential for cancer due to its antitumor properties. Curcumin's properties in treating various types of cancer have been reviewed in this systematic review based on *in vivo* studies.

Materials and methods: This systematic review focused on *in vivo* studies examining Curcumin's anti-cancer properties across a broad range of cancer types. PubMed, Google Scholar, and Scopus databases were searched to identify relevant articles. Researchers selected studies evaluating Curcumin's effects on cancer progression and development based on animal models. Final analyses were conducted on the data obtained from the selected articles. The included studies were published between 2000 and 2023.

Results: The current systematic review was based on 53 articles out of 412 eligible studies, which were selected from 770 articles of literature screened from 2000 to 2023. Based on this review, *in vivo* studies have demonstrated that curcumin can potentially treat various cancers. There is evidence that curcumin has significant anti-cancer properties, including tumor growth inhibition, metastasis inhibitory activity, and angiogenesis. Several studies have demonstrated the versatility and potential of curcumin in treating cancer.

Conclusion: Curcumin has considerable cancer treatment potential, based on the *in-vivo* studies. For curcumin to be considered an effective cancer therapy, further clinical research is needed between preclinical and clinical trials.

1. Introduction

One of the most significant public health problems in the world is cancer, which is the second life-threatening disease. The United States alone has seen more than 609,000 cancer deaths in 2018, with approximately 1.73 million new cases in 2018^{1,2}. Although cancer therapy has been improved in recent decades, the incidence of mortality of cancer did not decline^{3,4}. The prevention and treatment of cancer require understanding how molecular changes contribute to its

development and progression. Targeting specific cancer cells is the most common strategy for inhibiting tumor growth, metastasis, and progression without causing severe side effects³. In recent years, evidence has accumulated that some infectious agents are capable of causing anti-tumor effects against different types of cancers, such as *Toxoplasma gondii*, *Trypanosoma cruzi*, *Trichinella spiralis*, and *Echinococcus granulosus*⁴⁻⁷. Herbal remedies play a vital

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role in veterinary medicine and medicine, offering natural solutions for inflammation and infectious diseases⁸. As well as chemically synthesized anti-cancer agents, several anti-cancer compounds have been extracted from plants with different modes of action, including *Taxus brevifolia*, *Betula alba*, *Erythroxylum previllei*, *Catharanthus roseus*, *Curcuma longa*, *Cephalotaxus*, *Phytosomes* species⁹⁻¹³. Curcumin is an essential component in turmeric plant rhizomes¹⁴. Curcumin and its derivatives have had bifunctional properties in the past two decades, such as antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects¹⁵. The anti-cancer properties of curcumin have been demonstrated *in vitro* and *in vivo* at all stages of cancer growth, including the disease's promotion and initiation¹⁶. It is difficult for curcumin to cross the cell membrane since it forms hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding interactions with the membrane lipids. As a result, curcumin levels remain very low throughout the cytoplasm¹⁷. Curcumin nano formulated can overcome these challenges and increase their bioavailability. There is a strong correlation between nanodrug entrapment and the structure used to carry the nanodrugs during manufacturing¹⁸. They play an essential role in drug distribution, affecting the release profile from a transporter in terms of volume and magnitude¹⁹. Encapsulation efficiency gauges the absorption or trapping of bioactive compounds in nanostructures. It also indicates the speed of medication binding, correlating with the drug-to-carrier ratio. According to studies, nanotherapeutic increase curcumin's function *in vitro* and *in vivo* polymers, cyclodextrins, micelles, liposomes, conjugates, dendrimers, and nanostructures²⁰⁻²². The first focus was on enhancing the absorption rate constant of curcumin²². Later, they emphasized targeting curcumin in diseased areas using antibodies, peptides, or aptamers²³. A study was conducted to investigate the oral bioavailability of curcumin encapsulated within biodegradable poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) nanomaterials, and it found that nano curcumin was nine times more effective than unencapsulated curcumin in treating various conditions²⁴. Studies have also shown that nano curcumin is effective against liver and cardiac diseases, brain tumors, and cancerous lesions^{25, 26}. A wide range of pharmacological properties of curcumin have been reported in recent studies, including its benefits against type II diabetes, Alzheimer's disease, multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, and atherosclerosis²⁷⁻³⁰. Curcumin suppresses thrombosis and inhibits the replication of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and platelet aggregation³¹. Curcumin prevents liver damage, cataract development, pulmonary toxicity, and fibrosis by enhancing wound healing³²⁻³⁴. According to studies, curcumin is an effective treatment and prevention agent for a wide range of cancers, including gastrointestinal, breast, melanoma, hematological, colorectal, lung, neurological, head and neck, and sarcoma³⁵⁻³⁷. This systemic review aimed to investigate the immunomodulatory effects of curcumin in cancer treatments.

2. Materials and Methods

The purpose of this study is, using a systematic review

methodology to highlight the immunomodulatory properties of curcumin, with the latest research suggesting its effectiveness in the treatment of various types of cancer. Data bases such as SID, Magran, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, used to extract the findings from those studies. Several databases were searched extensively, and results were selected based on keywords. Keywords included curcumin, *in vivo*, and cancer. Other search terms used in this study were "colorectal cancer," "lung cancer," "turmeric extract," and "prostate cancer," "breast cancer,". The reference lists of systematic reviews and relevant articles were reviewed to ensure the search was comprehensive. A standardized form for data extraction was used, including study characteristics (author, study design publication year), experimental details (such as treatment durations, animal models, curcumin dosages), outcomes of interest (such as tumor size molecular pathways, apoptosis rates,), and other side effects. The current systematic review was based on 53 articles out of 412 eligible studies selected from 770 articles of literature screened from 2000 to 2023. A systematic review excludes unpublished data, duplicate papers, and abstracts of congress proceedings (Figure 1).

3. What is curcumin?

Turmeric is a rhizome from *Curcuma longa* Linn herb that has many uses for preventing and treating disease³⁸. There are numerous curcuminoids in turmeric powder, including bisdemethoxycurcumin (3%), demethoxycurcumin (17%), curcumin (77%), and others (3%)³⁹. Curcumin is a polyphenol (1,7-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,6-heptadiene-3,5-dione)⁴⁰. Curcumin treats a wide range of diseases, including asthma, allergies, coughs, bronchial hyperactivity, sinusitis, anorexia, coryza, and hepatitis⁴¹. Many studies show its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-infectious, hepatoprotective, thrombosuppressive, cardioprotective, chemopreventive, anti-arthritis, and anticarcinogenic properties^{42, 43}. Curcumin has also modulated several molecular targets in the body. Curcumin and its analogs have also been found in the *Costus speciosus*, *Curcuma mangga*, *Curcuma zedoaria*, *Curcuma phaeocaulis*, *Curcuma xanthorrhiza*, *Curcuma aromatic*, *Zingiber cassumunar plants*, and *Etlingera elatior*⁴⁴.

3.1. Bioavailability of curcumin

Even though curcumin has excellent potential for treating cancer diseases, its bioavailability, and low solubility in water have limited its clinical development. Clinical trials have indicated that when curcumin is administered orally for 8 grams daily, it rapidly transforms into metabolites, resulting in a low level of free curcumin in plasma (5ng/mL)⁴⁵. Numerous efforts have been made to improve curcumin's solubility, stability, and bioavailability. Chemical synthesis or Chemical modifications of its analogs have been adopted as a strategy for achieving derivatives of curcumin. The molecule's oxyphenyl and carbon chain

components are crucial for its anti-tumor effects. Many studies have focused on chemically changing the abovementioned key sites, obtaining promising results^{46, 47}.

For instance, reduced viability of MCF-7 cells and increased oral bioavailability of the compound have been reported⁴⁸.

Figure 1. The methodology of the current systematic review to extract information from relevant studies published in national and international databases.

There has been evidence that two promising nano curcumin formulations, LipocurcTM (liposomal curcumin for infusion) and Meriva® have increased the bioavailability of curcumin and improved clinical outcomes in patients with pancreatic cancer and lymphocytic leukemia⁴⁹⁻⁵¹. In 50 chronic myeloid leukemia patients, curcumin and imatinib (tyrosine kinase inhibitor) were evaluated for their therapeutic effects⁵². The mixed treatment was more effective than imatinib alone, although further research is needed to confirm its properties.

4. Mechanism of curcumin as an anti-cancer agent

4.1. Curcumin and adhesion molecules

An imbalance between cell death and proliferation is a major contributor to cancer, as uncontrolled cell proliferation, with cells evading death, can lead to various types of cancer⁵³. Apoptotic signals are generated through extrinsic and intrinsic pathways. The intrinsic pathway inhibits the expression of B-cell lymphoma 2 (Bcl-2), and B-cell lymphoma-extra-large by induction of the mitochondrial membrane⁵⁴. There is evidence that curcumin can disrupt the balance of mitochondrial membrane potential, thereby increasing the suppression of Bcl-xL in the mitochondria⁵⁵. Alternatively, the extrinsic apoptotic pathway induces apoptosis associated with

stimulating Death Receptors (DRs) and Tumor Necrosis Factor (TNF). As part of this pathway, curcumin is responsible for upregulating the expression of DR4 and DR5⁵⁶. Studies *in vivo* have suggested that curcumin and its derivatives can stimulate apoptosis in various cell lines by suppressing or downregulating intracellular transcription factors^{57, 58}. The transcription factors involved in these pathways include Cyclooxygenase II (COX-2), Matrix Metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9), Nuclear Factor-Kappa B (NF-κB), Signal Transducer and Activator of Transcription 3 (STAT3), Activator Protein 1 (AP-1), and nitric oxide synthase^{59, 60}. Additionally, curcumin may exert its anti-cancer effect by inhibiting lactate production and glucose uptake in cancer cells by inhibiting Pyruvate Kinase M2 (PKM2)⁶¹. A method of suppressing PKM2 was effective by inhibiting the Mammalian Target of Rapamycin-Hypoxia-Inducible Factor 1α (mTOR-HIF1α)⁶². Curcumin induces apoptosis in CL-5 xenograft tumors and reduction in cyclin D1, Mesenchymal Epithelial Transition Factor (c-Met), Akt, and Epidermal Growth Factor Receptors (EGFRs)^{63, 64}. Curcumin reduced lung-cell invasion and metastasis by upregulating HLJ1 expression in cancer cells⁶⁵. Along with the activity of curcumin on Nuclear Factor-κB (NF-κB) and STAT3 signaling cascades, curcumin also suppressed cell cycle arrest and cell proliferation and induced apoptosis by modulating other transcription factors, including Notch-1, Erg-1, PPAR-α, p53, Hif-1, β-catenin, and AP-1^{66, 67}. Researchers have demonstrated that curcumin inhibits the

phosphorylation of Focal Adhesion Kinase (FAK) and increases the expression of multiple Extra Cellular Matrix (ECM) components, which play a role in the metastasis and invasion of cancer cells⁶⁷. These findings suggest that curcumin inhibits the action of FAK by suppressing its phosphorylation sites, improving cell adhesion, and ultimately preventing cancer cells from migrating and detaching⁶⁸. According to one study by Zhou et al.⁶⁹, curcumin-associated compounds (containing benzyl piperidone moieties) showed activity in various cancer cell lines. They also found that some of these compounds inhibited the phosphorylation of extracellular signal-regulated kinases (Erk) 1/2 and phosphorylation of Akt. As a result of FAK suppression, cell adhesion was increased, eventually contributing to curcumin's anti-invasive properties. Curcumin reduced the expression of CD24 in colorectal cancer cells in a dose-dependent⁷⁰. The expression of E-cadherin was increased by curcumin, which suppressed epithelial-mesenchymal transition. A study in colorectal cancer cells has shown that curcumin inhibits metastasis by downregulating CD24, FAK, and Sp-1 expression and stimulating E-cadherin expression⁷¹. Apoptosis in hepatocellular carcinoma cells and epithelial ovarian tumor cells may be triggered by the curcumin analog B19, and autophagy and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress may play a significant role in the process^{72, 73}. It has been suggested that autophagy suppression may increase apoptosis induced by curcumin analogs by causing severe ER stress⁷⁴. Curcumin analogs also induce autophagy and ER stress in ovarian cancer cell lines⁷⁵.

Several extracellular matrix components, which play an essential role in invasion and metastasis, are enhanced by curcumin, including FAK phosphorylation⁷⁶. Curcumin may inhibit metastasis in colorectal cancer by down-regulating Sp-1, FAK, and CD24 and increasing E-cadherin expression⁷⁷.

4.2. Curcumin and endoplasmic reticulum

The Endoplasmic Reticulum (ER) is crucial to proteins' cellular synthesis and maturation. Various pathological conditions have been shown to interfere with the homeostasis of the ER and impair protein folding, causing an imbalance in the capacity and load of the ER to fold proteins and resulting in the accumulation of misfolded and unfolded proteins⁷⁸. The condition is commonly referred to as ER stress. The autophagy pathway is a conserved proteolysis pathway in eukaryotes⁷⁹. In addition to being an essential survival mechanism under metabolic stress, autophagy plays a critical role in protein homeostasis⁸⁰. Protease-associated degradation and autophagy-activated autophagy are two pathways by which the proteasome degrades ubiquitinated proteins. In addition to regulating cellular homeostasis, autophagy has been shown to prevent cell damage and protect cells from nutrient deprivation⁸¹. Recent studies have demonstrated that unfolded protein response signaling may also significantly impact interactions within the microenvironment of cancer cells^{82, 83}. It has been shown that folding proteins, autophagy, and ER stress-induced apoptosis are associated with cancer

cell proliferation⁸⁴. Anti-cancer treatments may activate this signaling pathway, possibly enhancing cancer cell death or chemotherapy resistance⁸⁵. According to recent data, curcumin analog B19 induces apoptosis through ER stress and autophagy in epithelial ovarian tumor cells and hepatocellular carcinoma cells⁸⁶. As a result of severe ER stress caused by autophagy inhibition, curcumin analogue-induced apoptosis may be increased. Curcumin analogs may induce apoptosis, ER stress, and autophagy *in vitro* in ovarian cancer cells⁷⁵. A recent study found that curcumin inhibited the growth of gliomas by activating autophagy, a type II programmed cell death⁷⁴.

4.3. Curcumin and Sp-1

The transcription factor Sp-1 is highly expressed in breast, gastric, and thyroid tumor cells⁸⁷. Studies showed that this transcription factor can interact with both a co-activator and co-repressor and, as a result, activate multiple specific biological functions, including the cell cycle and carcinogenesis^{88, 89}. It is essential for interacting nuclear factors with proteins and binding sequence-specific DNA binding. Several housekeeping genes, including urokinase plasminogen activator receptors (uPARs), vascular epithelial growth factors (VEGF), epithelial growth factor receptors (EGFR), and urokinase plasminogen activator (uPA), are known to influence cell differentiation, metastasis, and tumor angiogenesis^{90, 91}. Further, inhibiting Sp-1 and its housekeeping genes may provide a valuable hypothesis for preventing metastases, formation, and invasion^{65, 67}. As reported in a recent study, curcumin inhibits Sp-1 activation and downstream genes, such as ADEM10, calmodulin (CALM), SEPP1, and EPHB2, according to a concentration-dependent mechanism in colorectal cancer cell lines⁹². According to other studies, curcumin suppresses Sp-1 activity in bladder cancer cells and reduces Sp-1 DNA binding activity in Non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC)⁹³.

5. Anti-cancer activity of curcumin

The imbalance between cell proliferation and death, caused by the absence of apoptotic signals, contributes to various types of cancer as cells undergo uncontrolled proliferation⁹⁴. Studies *in vivo* have demonstrated that curcumin and its derivatives inhibit or downregulate the activity of intracellular transcription factors, thereby causing apoptosis in different cell lines⁹⁵. Several studies have identified curcumin and its derivatives as potential anti-cancer agents by interacting with various molecular targets^{92, 96}. It has been shown that it can suppress the growth and proliferation of cancer cells in a variety of cancer types, including breast, prostate, lung, and colorectal cancer⁹⁷. The following section summarizes data from *in vitro* and animal studies reporting curcumin and its derivatives' anti-cancer effects.

5.1. Prostate cancer

Both *in vitro* and *in vivo*, curcumin has demonstrated a solid ability to inhibit prostate cell proliferation and induce

apoptosis through interference with several cellular pathways, including Epidermal Growth Factor Receptors (EGFRs), Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases (MAPKs), and nuclear factor κ (NF κ B)⁹⁸. A recent study has revealed that curcumin can activate Protein kinase D1 (PKD1), which attenuates oncogenic signaling by β -catenin and MAPK, ultimately inhibiting prostate cancer⁹⁹. The PKD1 expression was significantly downregulated after prostate cancer transitioned from an androgen-dependent to an androgen-independent state, as well as to affect prostate cancer invasion and motility through its interaction with E-cadherin¹⁰⁰. Thus, it has been considered as a potential new therapeutic target for the treatment of cancer in general as well as prostate cancer in particular¹⁰¹. Other curcumin derivatives have also been shown to have anti-cancer properties against prostate cancer in addition to curcumin^{37, 102, 103}. As can be seen in Figure 2, DNA complexes conjugated with metallocurcumin exhibited significant toxicity against prostate cancer cells (LNCaP, DU145, PC3, 22Rv1, and TRAMP-C1)¹⁰⁴.

5.2. Colorectal cancer

As the third most common form of cancer, colorectal cancer ranks third behind lung and prostate cancer¹⁰⁵. Although colorectal carcinoma patients undergo surgery and chemotherapy to remove tumor tissue, more than half suffer recurrences. There was a reduction in M (1) G levels

binding to the *miR-21* promoter, inhibiting overexpression of *miR-21* in colorectal cancer cells¹⁰⁷. Through *miR-21* gene regulation, curcumin inhibited tumor tissue growth by arresting the cell cycle in the G2/M phase in HCT 116 colorectal cancer cells¹⁰⁷. According to an *in vivo* study conducted on mice with colorectal cancer, curcumin was more effective than radiation therapy when combined with radiation as it can target Nuclear Factor (NF)¹⁰⁸.

5.3. Breast Cancer

There has been an alarming increase in breast cancer death rates among women over the past few decades¹⁰⁹. According to a meta-analysis of 21 retrospective studies, breast cancer recurrence rates are still high despite chemotherapy, lumpectomy, radiation therapy, and endocrine therapy¹¹⁰. As a result, more effective therapeutic strategies are still needed. According to a study involving MCF-7 breast cancer cells and MCF-10A human mammary epithelial cells, curcumin treatment substantially reduced telomerase activity¹¹¹. This effect was correlated with curcumin's ability to downregulate hTERT but not via the c-Myc mRNA pathway. Curcumin's effects on matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), cell proliferation regulation proteins, and nuclear factor-B have been evaluated in BT-483 and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell lines¹¹². After treatment with curcumin, it was observed that cyclic D1 levels in MDA-MB-231 cells and CDK4 levels in BT-483 cell lines decreased. Similar to previous studies on other breast cancer cell lines, this study confirms that curcumin inhibits proliferation by downregulating NF-B. The combination of arabinogalactan and curcumin-induced apoptosis in MDA-MB-231 cells by increasing ROS levels, disrupting mitochondrial membranes, and decreasing glutathione levels^{113, 114}. Additionally, curcumin inhibits breast tumor growth by overexpressing the *p53* gene and reducing levels of antigen ki-67¹¹⁵. Moreover, curcumin has also been shown to inhibit the production of inflammatory cytokines CXCL1/2 in MDA-MB-231 cells¹¹⁶. As a result of curcumin inhibiting CXCL1 and 2, multiple metastasis-promoting genes, such as CXCR4, are inhibited. Furthermore, dimethyl curcumin (ASC-J9) inhibits several types of steroid receptors, which may be effective in treating estrogen-dependent breast cancer^{117, 118}.

5.4. Lung cancer

A lung cancer diagnosis is one of the most common cancer diagnoses among men and the third most common among women¹¹⁹. In addition to surgery, chemotherapy, radiation therapy, and immunotherapy are all standard treatments for lung cancer¹²⁰. A study of the therapeutic potential of turmeric in lung cancer therapy showed that it acts on a Wnt/ β -catenin-dependent pathway in the human lung cancer cell line A549¹²¹. In the same cell line, curcumin suppresses the expression of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) and NF- κ B expression¹²². In lung cancer cells, Curcumin inhibited the Enhancer of Zest Homolog 2 (EZH2) expression, decreasing Notch 1 expression¹²³. Various

Figure 2. Curcumin's multilayered impact on prostate cancer. The figure highlights the modulation of crucial cellular pathways such as mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), and nuclear factor κ (NF κ B) by curcumin, showcasing its multifaceted effects on prostate cancer cells. The diagram further details the activation of Protein Kinase D1 (PKD1) by curcumin, elucidating its role in attenuating oncogenic signaling, particularly in the context of β -catenin and MAPK pathways. Additionally, the figure represents the specific action of curcumin in enhancing androgen receptor degradation in androgen-dependent prostate cancer. Furthermore, the visual illustrates the toxic impact of Metallo-curcumin conjugated DNA complexes on prostate cancer cells, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse strategies employed by curcumin in combating prostate cancer at the molecular level.

in cancer colorectal cells when curcumin was administered without affecting COX-2 protein levels¹⁰⁶. Additionally, curcumin treatment inhibited AP-1 (activator protein) from

studies have demonstrated that curcumin inhibits cell proliferation, increases apoptosis, and prevents the G2/M phase of Non-Small-Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC). Furthermore, curcumin produces Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS), which activates the DNA damage signaling pathway¹²⁴. In a recent study, a low dose of curcumin was administered to NSCLC cells for an extended period. Metastatic and invasion potential of the cancer cells was significantly suppressed in curcumin at doses range of 0.25-0.5 M¹²⁵. Using curcumin derivatives against NSCLC cells with ALK rearrangements has also shown promising results, even when those cells become resistant to ALK inhibitors¹²⁶. Cancer cells are sensitive to chemotherapeutic agents due to the extracellular signal-regulated kinase pathway (ERK). Curcumin's selective targeting of it causes a 75% reduction in the expression of ERK $\frac{1}{2}$ ^{127,128}. Phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K)/Akt-dependent pathways are associated with cell proliferation and apoptosis in several cancer cell lines, but the available data regarding the relationship between PI3K/Akt pathways and apoptosis are inconsistent¹²⁹. Some drugs induce apoptosis in cancer cells by stimulating this pathway, while others inhibit it. The new curcumin derivative T59 has been shown to activate PI3K/Akt and induce apoptosis in lung cancer cells¹³⁰. However, another study found that curcumin, combined with Paris Saponin 2 (PS2), inhibited the PI3K-Akt pathway and induced apoptosis¹³¹.

6. Potential side effects of curcumin

According to the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA), curcumin is "generally safe." The literature does not indicate any significant side effects associated with curcumin¹³². It has been documented that some of the side effects are reversible, including allergic dermatitis¹³³. According to the results of dose-escalation studies, consuming up to 12 grams of curcumin daily has no adverse effects¹³⁴. When curcumin was administered to patients with solid tumors orally at 900 mg/day for eight weeks, no adverse effects were reported except mild gastrointestinal discomfort¹³⁵. Patients with breast cancer also reported no adverse effects from taking 6 grams of curcumin every day for seven weeks, and prostate cancer patients reported no adverse effects from 3 grams of curcumin taken daily for nine weeks¹³⁶. The curcumin compound also exhibits a strong ability to chelate iron¹³⁷. As a result of long-term curcumin supplementation in mice, iron depletion was enhanced when low-iron diets were fed to the mice¹³⁸. In addition, curcumin is an anticoagulant and is likely to cause bleeding time to increase in patients taking anticoagulants¹³⁹. While curcumin has no overt adverse effects, several P450 subtypes, including CYP2C9 and CYP3A4, have been reported to be inhibited by this compound¹⁴⁰. Therefore, curcumin may interact with other medications, such as antibiotics, antidepressants, and anticoagulants. A warfarin and clopidogrel pharmacokinetics study in Wistar rats found that curcumin increased the elimination half-life and distribution volume of norfloxacin¹⁴¹.

7. Therapeutic activity of curcumin nanoformulations

Several curcumin nanoformulations have been developed so far. Most nanoformulations have improved curcumin's solubility and bioavailability while protecting it from hydrolysis inactivation¹⁴². Most nanoformulations focus on intracellular delivery and long-term drug retention, while some concentrate on prolonged circulation and retention. Nanoformulations used to improve the retention and circulation of drugs within the body, whereas others have been developed to enhance intracellular delivery¹⁴³.

7.1. Liposomes

A liposome is a spherical vesicle composed of multiple or single phospholipid bilayers that closely resemble the structure of a cell membrane¹⁴⁴. The liposome is a perfect delivery vehicle for biologically active substances *in vitro* and *in vivo*¹⁴⁵. Liposomes provide several advantages, including excellent stability, controlled distribution, easy preparation, high biodegradability, biocompatibility, targeting specific cells, flexibility, better solubility, and minimal toxicity¹⁴⁶. Therefore, scientists consider liposomes to be the most effective drug-carrier system, and they are preferred by many. The number and size of bilayers influence liposomal drug encapsulation in the liposome. Thus, the size of the vesicle is a crucial factor in estimating liposome circulation time. The diameter of liposomes ranges from 2.5 to 25 nm¹⁴⁷. According to numerous studies, liposomes help dissolve curcumin in phospholipid bilayers, allowing curcumin to be dispersed across aqueous media and enhancing curcumin's effectiveness¹⁴⁸. Moreover, liposomal drugs accumulate mainly in the bone marrow, spleen, lung, liver, and other tissues and organs. As a result, the side effects of drugs are further reduced, and their therapeutic index is improved. According to Dhule et al. 2012, liposomal curcumin demonstrated powerful anti-cancer effects *in vitro* and *in vivo* against breast cancer cell lines MCF-7 and KHOS OS¹⁴⁹. Research has examined curcumin liposomes' biochemical processes and antitumor activity in PC-3 human prostate cancer cells. Compared to free CUR, liposomes of CUR had a lower survival rate in PC-3 cells. Liposomes also absorbed curcumin more efficiently, resulting in a longer and higher fluorescence intensity than in the control group. In addition, reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction and western blot analyses were used to determine messenger RNA (mRNA) and matrix metalloproteinase-2 (MMP-2) levels. According to experiments, curcumin liposomes can facilitate the absorption of drug-loaded liposomes to enhance cytotoxic effects in PC-3 cells. MMP-2-mRNA levels and proteins decreased gradually after curcumin liposome concentrations increased along with MMP-2-mRNA levels. The MMP-2 concentration was simultaneously downregulated in PC-3 cells. Additionally, Tefas et al. 2017 formulated liposomes with Curcumin and doxorubicin, reducing cell proliferation in C26 murine colon cancer cells

and demonstrating enhanced cytotoxicity compared to free Curcumin¹⁵⁰.

An *in vitro* study has shown that liposomal curcumin stimulates apoptosis and dose-dependent growth suppression in two human colorectal cancer cell lines (including Colo205 and LoVo cells) by producing poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase and 3 (4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-5 (3-carboxymethoxyphenyl)-2-(4-sulfophenyl)-2H-tetrazolium salt¹⁵¹. Similarly, curcumin-encapsulated liposomes were highly encapsulating, predominantly polydisperse, and smaller in particle size. The use of blue light-emitting diodes (BLED) combined with curcumin liposome nanocarriers (LIP-CUR) was found to generate excellent anti-cancer effects and bioactivity (BLED-PDT)¹⁵². The study showed that aqueous-soluble F127-CUR is capable of mediating curcumin's anti-cancer action and can facilitate BLED-PDT-mediated apoptosis as well as mediating its anti-cancer action. The BLED-PDT activity of aqueous-soluble F127-CUR was higher in cancer cells than in those receiving free curcumin. Based on these findings, liposomes might be an effective carrier for curcumin⁶³.

7.2. Nanoparticles

A nanoparticle's diameter ranges from 1 to 100 nm, which makes it useful for drug delivery because of its unique biological, physical, and chemical properties¹⁵³. Nanoparticles are a thousand times smaller than average cells in the human body. The encapsulation of drugs within nanoparticles can enhance their solubility and pharmacokinetic properties, allowing them to be released, controlled, and targeted. Curcumin has been used with solid lipid, albumin, gold, magnetic, and polymer-based nanoparticles to improve therapeutic effects¹⁵⁴.

7.3. Conjugates

The conjugate complex is created when two or more molecules are combined, especially by a covalent bond. A hydrophilic polymer and small molecule conjugation of curcumin increases its solubility and oral bioavailability. In a study published by Manjuand Sreenivasan, curcumin conjugated with hyaluronic acid reduced the effects of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) and improved their aqueous stability¹⁵⁵. According to Muangnoi et al.¹⁵⁶, a curcumin-glutaric acid prodrug (CURDG) was created via ester linkages and evaluated in mouse cancer models. The gold nanoparticle-PVP-curcumin conjugate (PVP-C-AuNPs) has been shown to hinder the aggregation of A β (1-6) while facilitating prolonged drug release and enhancing curcumin bioavailability¹⁵⁷. The bioavailability of curcumin can be enhanced by piperine (an alkaloid derived from black pepper). Further, this alkaloid enhances compound absorption by forming brush borders on the intestinal lining¹⁵⁸. Piperine also inhibits UDP glucuronosyl

transferases and cytochrome p450s, which may affect cell metabolism. The action of piperine is also exerted on p-glycoproteins¹⁵⁹. Using piperine combined with curcumin significantly increased serum levels of curcumin in humans and animals by 2,000 times because of the extensive absorption and bioavailability. Several polycurcumins have been reported to be cytotoxic to cancer cells. However, there have been reports that polyacetal-based polycurcumins are more cytotoxic toward MCF-7 breast cancer cell lines and the SKOV-3 and OVCAR-3 ovarian cancer cells. Cancerous cells can also rapidly absorb them, where polyacetal-based polycurcumin is hydrolyzed and released as active curcumin. According to *in vitro* studies, it inhibited the G0/G1 phase of the cell cycle in SKOV-3 cells and stimulated the apoptosis of those cells partly via the caspase-3 pathway. The intravenous administration of polyacetal-based polycurcumin resulted in significant antitumor activity against SKOV-3 intraperitoneal xenografts¹⁶⁰.

7.4. Cyclodextrins (CD)

α -, β -, and γ -CDs are multi-component hybrid, soluble carrier systems for non-covalently bound drugs. These bucket-shaped oligosaccharides consist of 6 (α -), 7 (β -), or 8 (γ -) D-glucopyranose units linked via an α -1, 4-glycosidic bond to form macrocycles. Numerous researchers have demonstrated the role of CD in the delivery of curcumin in recent years¹⁶¹. The β -CD, γ -CD, and their derivatives were widely used due to their easy synthesis and low cost in the delivery of drugs and adaptability. Yallapu et al. 2010 demonstrated a significant increase in CUR distribution and therapeutic value in prostate cancer cells compared to unformulated CUR using a β -CD-facilitated curcumin drug delivery system¹⁶². Zhang et al. 2016 observed that the formulation of cyclodextrin with curcumin (CD15) caused lung cancer cells to experience cell cycle arrest and increased apoptosis compared to curcumin alone¹⁶³. Moreover, the experimental findings of this study indicated that CD15 enhances curcumin delivery and is effective in treating lung cancer. Nanoparticles were developed by hyaluronic acid, sulfobutyl-ether- β -cyclodextrin, and chitosan, without or with curcumin, and used to treat intestinal epithelial cells and colorectal cancer¹⁶⁴. According to the results of a study, curcumin nanoparticles were more stable and more effective at encapsulation. Additionally, it reduced the potency of curcumin as a cytotoxic agent in normal intestinal epithelial cells and reduced the proliferation of cancer cells. In retinitis pigmentosa, Curcumin and CD complexes mediated increased solubility and prolonged drug release. The findings assisted in formulating eye drops that are derived from natural phytochemicals. Zhang et al.¹⁶³ investigated the effects of curcumin-CDs on cellular uptake and anti-cancer activity. Compared to free curcumin, curcumin-CDs provided improved delivery of

Curcumin based therapies Applications

Figure 3. Curcumin in combination therapy for enhanced cancer treatment

curcumin and increased curcumin's therapeutic efficacy *in vivo* and *in vitro*¹⁶³. Therefore, curcumin -CDs inhibit CyclinE-CDK2 combinations, increase the p53/p21 signaling cascade, and elevate Bax/caspase-3 expression to induce G1-phase arrest and cellular apoptosis through the regulation of MAPK/NF- κ B signaling pathways. According to these findings, curcumin-CDs can improve the delivery of CUR to tumors and its therapeutic potential¹⁶³.

7.5. Metallo-Complexes

The palladium (II) complexes of curcumin (CUR) displayed potent antitumor activity against HeLa, A549 and MCF-7 cancer cells¹⁶⁵. Furthermore, further studies revealed that these complexes perturbed mitochondrial membrane potential, causing tumor cells to undergo apoptosis, and the cell cycle was arrested in the S phase. A study by Vellampatti et al.2018 found that metallo-CUR-conjugated DNA complexes exhibited significant toxic effects on prostate cancer cells compared to pristine DNA¹⁰⁴. A further study evaluated the cellular uptake of these complexes and found that DNA complexes containing Cu²⁺/Ni²⁺-CUR displayed brighter fluorescence than those containing Zn²⁺-CUR (Figure 3).

Illustrations depicting key aspects of curcumin-based therapies. In the first set, liposomal structures are detailed, emphasizing their phospholipid bilayer composition, curcumin encapsulation, targeted delivery to specific cells, and *in vivo* effects, showcasing reduced side effects and improved therapeutic index compared to free curcumin. The second set focuses on nanoparticles, showcasing their varied structures, drug delivery capabilities, and widespread use in improving curcumin's therapeutic applications. The third set explores cyclodextrins, highlighting their bucket-shaped structures, role in

curcumin delivery systems, and formation of water-soluble complexes, potentially enhancing curcumin's efficacy. The fourth set delves into metallo-complexes, outlining their structures, potent antitumor actions, ROS-dependent cascades, and cellular uptake mechanisms. Finally, the combination therapy set illustrates the conceptual framework, synergistic effects, cellular-level interactions, and potential clinical applications of combining curcumin with other therapeutic agents, offering a comprehensive view of the multi-faceted landscape of curcumin-based treatments.

8. Future challenges

While considerable effort has been made to improve curcumin's biological and physicochemical properties, several issues remain regarding the compound's bioavailability, specificity, and potency to the target tissues¹⁶⁶. Curcumin's pharmacological properties have not been significantly improved using medicinal chemistry approaches, nor have its derivatives demonstrated more potency than curcumin itself¹⁷. Because curcumin and its derivatives have low potency, higher doses need to be administered to achieve a therapeutic response, which results in increased adverse effects and poor patient compliance¹⁶⁷. Efficacy and solubility are also challenging to balance, and in most cases, one is sacrificed for the other during structural modification¹⁶⁸. Many structural modifications enhance curcumin's efficacy, reduce its solubility, and make it more hydrophobic^{169, 170}. To overcome this problem, it is required to conduct more studies. Various approaches have been used to improve curcumin's cellular uptake and efficacy, but most of these formulations have been at the proof-of-concept stage instead of clinical testing^{171, 172}. Before these curcumin

delivery systems can reach the pharmaceutical market, no clinical studies are designed to evaluate their safety and efficacy. Furthermore, most drug delivery systems developed for curcumin do not target a specific tissue. Curcumin delivery systems still need to be improved to enhance their selectivity for specific tumor types^{173,174}. As a result of tissue-specific delivery, curcumin concentrations are enhanced in the target tissue, resulting in improved efficacy (with lower doses) and fewer side effects^{175,176}.

9. Conclusion

This systematic review examined the availability of *in vivo* studies on using curcumin in treating colorectal, breast, lung, and prostate cancer. According to the combined evidence presented in the included studies, curcumin is potentially effective against various types of cancer, highlighting its numerous anti-cancer properties. Researchers have found that curcumin inhibits tumor growth, induces apoptosis, suppresses angiogenesis, and modulates several cellular signaling pathways against cancer. Considering its broad spectrum of action, curcumin may be used as a complementary treatment and an adjunct therapy for these common types of cancer. Although there were some limitations to this systematic review, it is important to acknowledge those limitations and challenges. As a result of this systematic review, curcumin has the potential to be a promising anti-cancer agent against colorectal, lung, prostate, and breast. It is essential to approach these results with cautious optimism to recognize the need to conduct further rigorous research to reduce the gap between preclinical promise and clinical application. It is clear that curcumin has excellent potential as a cancer treatment agent, and further study of its potential is warranted to achieve more effective and holistic cancer treatments.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors' contributions

Amir Reza Rashidzad primarily carried out the conceptualization of the project, while the initial writing and preparation of the original draft involved the collaborative efforts of Ghasem Dolatkhah Laein, Samin Safarian, and Saba Delasaeimarvi. Subsequently, the project underwent thorough review and editing, with contributions from Ghazale Sadat Ahmadi, Sima Dadfar, and Elahe Bakhshi. The project was self-funded, and Amir Reza Rashidzade supervised its development.

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Ethical considerations

All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed.

Availability of data and materials

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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